

ANN MODEL FOR 3D FEATURE STABILIZATION

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Abstract

Three-dimensional (3D) feature stabilization is a crucial aspect in various fields such as computer vision, robotics, and augmented reality. It is essential to maintain the stability of identified features across frames for accurate analysis and reliable performance. In this paper, we propose an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) model designed specifically for 3D feature stabilization tasks. Our model uses the inherent capacity of neural networks to learn complex patterns and relationships within sequential data to effectively stabilize 3D features across consecutive frames.

Keywords: ANN; 3D feature; stabilization; sigmoid.

Introduction

In the context of 3D video stabilization, the stabilization of 3D features plays a pivotal role in ensuring smooth and visually pleasing results [1-2]. By stabilizing features across the depth dimension, it can mitigate the effects of camera motion, thereby enhancing the overall stability and coherence of the 3D video sequence [3-5]. In recent years, the use of various neural network models has become popular in the field of 3D feature stabilization. There are various types of neural networks used in computing, including Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs), and others.

A Convolutional Neural Network (CNN or ConvNet) is a type of deep neural network that is mainly used for analyzing visual imagery [6]. They are also known as shift-invariant or area-invariant Artificial Neural Networks (SIANNs), based on their shared-weights design and translation invariance characteristics. CNNs have a wide range of applications, such as image and video recognition, recommender systems, image classification, medical image analysis, and language processing.

Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) belongs to the class of Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) where the connections between nodes form a graph oriented in a temporal sequence. This unique property enables the RNN to exhibit temporary dynamic behavior. With its internal state (memory), RNN can process sequences of varying lengths, making it useful in applications such as speech recognition, linked handwriting recognition, and others.

Artificial Neural Network (ANN), also known as Neural Networks (NNs), are computing systems inspired by the biological neural networks. ANNs can learn any nonlinear function and are commonly referred to as Universal Function Approximators. These networks have the ability to learn weights that map any input to output [7-8].

Fig. 1. Artificial Neural Network

Development of an ANN model for 3D feature stabilization

ANN, one of the neural networks mentioned above, was used to develop the ANN model for the 3D feature stabilization process.

Fig. 2. ANN model for 3D feature stabilization

Figure 2 depicts the detailed flow chart of the ANN-based model used for stabilizing 3D features.

Neural networks use activation functions to transform the summed weighted input from the node into its output or activation. There are several types of activation functions used in neural networks. The ANN-based model proposed for 3D feature stabilization employed the sigmoid activation function.

A sigmoid function is one type of mathematical function that has a characteristic "S"-shaped curve or sigmoid curve. The sigmoid activation function has a mathematical form $\sigma(x) = \frac{1}{(1+e^{-x})}$ and is shown in Figure 3. It takes a real value and "squeezes" in the range from 0 to 1.

In particular, large negative numbers are equal to 0 and large positive numbers are equal to 1. Usually used in output layer of a binary classification, where result is either 0 or 1, as value for sigmoid function lies between 0 and 1 only so, result can be predicted easily to be 1 if value is greater than 0.5 and 0 otherwise. The sigmoid function is historically frequently used because it is “the rate at which a neuron shoots: from total non-shooting (0) to fully saturated shooting at the predicted maximum frequency (1).

Fig. 3. Sigmoid activation function

The main reason for using the sigmoid function is that it exists between (0 to 1). It is therefore especially used for models where it has to assume probability as an output. The sigmoid is the right choice because the probability of anything is only between 0 and 1. The function can be distinguished. Hence, it can be found the sigmoidal curve at any two points. The function is monotonic, but the product of the function is not.

The proposed model has 24 inputs and 12 outputs. The proposed model consists of one hidden layer (see Figure 2). The hidden layer is based on the Sigmoid activation function. The hidden layer consists of 12 neurons.

The proposed model was implemented using an Artificial Neural Network (ANN), which involves several processes. One of these processes is the feed-forwarding process, also known as the perceptron network process. In this process, the output of all neurons passes to the next layers, but not to the previous ones, creating a one-way flow. During the training phase, which is a feedback system, connections are established.

The feed-forwarding process can be expressed using equations in the following sequence.

First of all, denoting is done in the ANN-based model (see Figure 2). x_j is equal to $out_{1,j}$. Here j can take numbers from 1 to 12.

$$out_{1,j} = x_j \quad (1)$$

All activation functions, fact1 and fact2 are equal to each other. This equation is denoted by $\sigma(x)$. $\sigma(x)$ denotes the sigmoid activation function. For finding the sigmoid activation function is given by the following equation.

$$fact1 = fact2 = \sigma(x) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-x}} \quad (2)$$

Next, $out_{2,k}$ is found using $fact1$ and $out_{1,j}$.

$$out_{2,k} = fact1 \left(\left[\sum_{j=1}^{12} out_{1,j} \cdot w_{1,j,k} \right] + b_{1,k} \right) = fact1 \left(\left[\sum_{j=1}^{12} x_j \cdot w_{1,j,k} \right] + b_{1,k} \right)$$

(3)

$out_{2,k}$ denotes the output of the hidden layer. $out_{2,k}$ indicates that it consists of k hidden layers. In hidden layer, there are 12 neurons. Therefore k is a range from 1 to 12. The output of each neuron in $out_{2,k}$ means that the sum of the outputs of the previous layer multiplied by the outputs of previous layer is added to the bias and activation function.

y_n is obtained using the following equation:

$$y_m = f_{act3} \left(\left[\sum_{k=1}^{12} out_{3,k} \cdot w_{3,k,m} \right] + b_{3,m} \right) \quad (4)$$

y_n denotes the output of the hidden layer. y_n means that the sum of the outputs of hidden layer multiplied by the outputs of hidden layer is added to the bias and activation function. y_n can be expressed by equation as follows:

$$y_m = f_{act2} \left(\left[\sum_{k=1}^9 f_{act1} \left(\left[\sum_{j=1}^{12} x_j \cdot w_{1,j,k} \right] + b_{1,k} \right) \cdot w_{2,k,m} \right] + b_{2,m} \right)$$

(5)

By expressing $out_{2,k}$ through x_j , y_n can be expressed using the following equation.

$$y_n = f_{act3} \left(\left[\sum_{m=1}^9 f_{act2} \left(\left[\sum_{k=1}^9 f_{act1} \left(\left[\sum_{j=1}^{12} x_j \cdot w_{1,j,k} \right] + b_{1,k} \right) \cdot w_{2,k,m} \right] + b_{2,m} \right) \times w_{3,m,n} \right] + b_{3,n} \right) \quad (6)$$

y_n can be expressed by the action function as follows:

$$y_m = \left[1 + e^{-\left(\left[\sum_{k=1}^{12} \frac{w_{2,k,m}}{1 + e^{-\left(\left[\sum_{j=1}^{12} x_j \cdot w_{1,j,k} \right] + b_k \right)}} \right] + b_m \right)} \right]^{-1}$$

Conclusion

In our study, we present a new Artificial Neural Network (ANN) model designed specifically for stabilizing 3D features between successive frames. In our future work, we plan to demonstrate, through the utilization of simple neural network architectures and methodologies, the efficacy of our model in effectively stabilizing 3D features amidst various challenges such as motion, occlusion, and environmental changes.

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